

MULTIVARIATE COMPETITIVE POSITION ANALYSIS IN BANKING SECTOR: POLISH BANKS VERSUS PEER GROUP PERSPECTIVE

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Banks perform various roles in the economy and are critical to both the financial system and the real economy. Situation of banks has changed when compare financial ratios before and after financial crisis. The paper presents the possibility of using euclidean distance from the Positive Development Pattern (PDP) to identify those Polish banks which has the highest competitive position comparing to domestic banking sector and peer group of main competitors. As a result there was created synthetic ratio with range from 0 to 1 for each of bank. Sorted from highest to lowest value of SMD ratio became a ranking of competitive position of banks. The purpose of the paper is to present possibility of usage of multidimensional analysis to evaluate the competitive position of bank versus peer group in 2007 and 2013. Author presents SMD (Systematic Measure of Development) ratio as a tool that solves the problem of low level of utility of one-dimensional analysis.

competitive, advantage, taxonomy, bank, multidimensional analysis

1. Introduction

Banks provide various roles in the banking sector and are critical to both the financial system and the real economy. In particular, they improve the problem of asymmetric information between investors and borrowers thus channeling savings into investments. They also provide risk sharing by intertemporal smoothing of undiversifiable risk as well as insurance to depositors against unexpected consumption shocks. They also contribute to the growth of the economy [1]. Banks are public companies quoted on the stock exchange and are subject of the value based management concepts as any other entity. Unfortunately, contemporary banks due to connections with global financial markets can contribute to the emergence of a major financial crisis, as it was in 2007.

The source of the 2007 financial crisis in the US and some EU countries was the mechanism of mortgage banking expansion. It was generating erroneous conditions for the risk management, mainly due to the overvaluation of the mortgage protections. In the era of globalization of financial markets the main channel of spreading of the crisis beyond financial institutions was securitization of mortgage loans. Securitization causes effects between sectoral and cross-border through MBS (Mortgage Backed Securities), CDO's (Col-

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lateralized Debt Obligations) and also a mortgage bonds and SIV (Structured Investment Vehicles).

The 2007 financial crisis shocked world's economic system. GDP is still below its pre-crisis peak in many rich countries, especially in Europe, where the financial crisis has evolved into the euro crisis. The effects of the crash are still rippling through the world economy. With half a decade's hindsight, it is clear the crisis had multiple causes. The most obvious is the financiers themselves especially the irrationally exuberant Anglo-Saxon sort, who claimed to have found a way to banish risk when in fact they had simply lost track of it. Central bankers and other regulators also bear blame, for it was they who tolerated this folly [2]. Before, during and after financial crisis situation of small banks was better than big global banks [3], [4]. Since August 2007 there has been a loss of value of companies on the world stock exchanges in the amount of more than 16 trillion euros, which is equivalent to 150% of GDP across the European Union [5]. During the crisis we reported enormous loss of banks market value. For example Allied of Irish Banks lost 97,1% of market value, The Royal Bank of Scotland lost 95,5%, Fortis Bank lost 94,1%, Commerzbank lost 91,4%, Deutsche Bank lost 82,5% and UniCredit lost 82,1%.

Nowadays the banking sector is global and it is characterized by intense and constantly growing competition. Mega-banks in the world have been expanding over the last decades, also through the process of mergers and acquisitions. Today functioning of mega-banks is related to several problems. For example total assets of 20 biggest banks in 2007 (before "subprime crisis") was about 22 trillion USD, which represented about 40% of the Gross World Product (which was about 54 trillion USD). This demonstrates the scale of the involvement of the largest banking institutions in the global economy. At the end of 2011, after four years of sub-prime crisis in the financial markets (where risk concerned entire economies), total assets of the 20 largest banks accounted for about 27 trillion of USD which represents about 34% of the Gross World Product. It is worth noting that the 20 largest banks in the world with the end of 2011, manages the assets representing 26% of total assets in 1000 of the largest banks in the world (total assets of the 1000 largest banks in the world in 2011 was 101.6 trillion USD). The importance of the problem may indicate that two German banks in 2011 have assets equal to 105 % of the GDP of the Germany. In the same year three French banks had assets at the level of 174 % of French GDP [6]. It is clear that one cannot compare small local banks (like in Polish banking sector) to mega, big or even medium global banks. In this paper author presents multivariate competitive position analysis of Polish banks. Due to the nature of the Polish economy and banking sector the research concerned peer group construction from the small banks point of view. Small banks, can succeed only in local markets. It is estimated that in Europe small banks constitute about 24% of the total [7]. The role and characteristics of small banks (also in terms of competition) have been explored in the international literature and have been the subject matter of many studies [8], [9], [7], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. The purpose of this paper is to present possibility of usage of multivariate (multi-dimensional) analysis to evaluate the competitive position of banks. The paper presents the possibility of using euclidean distance from the Positive Development Pattern (PDP) to

identify those banks, which are characterized by the highest competitive position. The following reflections are embedded in the mainstream of theory of Value Based Management (VBM).

2. Competition advantage and theory of Value Based Management

Value Based Management refers to the corporate objective of increasing the wealth of the shareholders and stakeholders of a company. The concept of competitive advantage has been presented for a long time in the literature of corporate finance [15], [16], [17]. Among the causes of the 2007 global financial crisis there is mentioned macroeconomic factors, institutional, regulatory, and even features of the nature of management (avarice, greed, selfishness). Management concepts for some time has remained outside the wave of criticism. Shortly after the crisis appeared stating that it was concept of VBM implemented in banks contributed to the crisis. Recognising the concept of VBM as a major cause of the financial crisis however is dangerous for several reasons. VBM creates an efficient and comprehensive system together with the established management instruments and tools, which cannot be blamed for the manner of its use. The effectiveness and efficiency of VBM concept is based on professional management skills, the degree of organization companies, organizational culture, infrastructure, as well as general conditions management. Development potential of banks which launched globalization, liberalization and deregulation of the system encountered no leveling mechanisms the emerging of direct and future threats.

In VBM theory the concept of competitive advantage appears in value drivers verification. The first value driver presented by Alfred Rappaport in 1985 was a value growth period convergent to the period in which the company is able to maintain a competitive advantage (competitive position of the leader) in the industry. Competitive advantage is a source of above-average business performance in the long term [18] and is a key element in the process of formulating the company's strategy [19], [18]. Competitive advantage also appears when the company implements the strategy contributes to value creation and competitors are not able to achieve similar benefits [20]. In VBM theory there is also separate part for such specific institutions like banks. This is due to the specific nature of the bank as a financial intermediary and its ability to generate systemic risk. Main purpose of VBM is to create value. To create value in banking there is necessity to identify bank's value drivers. Value drivers are related to Critical Success Factors (CSF) and Key Performing Indicators (KPI). These concepts in the end translate into the problem of choosing the indicator (ratio) that will be evaluated.

There is no doubt that multidimensional (multivariate) analysis has more advantages than one-dimensional analysis. It allows to compare objects considering more indicators taken into account at the same time. Data of Polish banks and peer group for Polish banks were based on *Bureau van Dijk* data base. Construction of peer group for researched banks allowed to compare competitive position of an object to its competitor. Methodology of competitor selection took into account the specificity of the Polish banking sector versus Western European competitors. On the one hand, Polish banks have relatively low

value of assets, on the other hand, they have a relatively high level of stability from the risk point of view. It was the basis for the selection of indicators to the study.

3. Methodology

The paper presents the possibility of using euclidean distance from the Positive Development Pattern (PDP) to identify those banks, which are characterized by the highest competitive position. The procedure consisted of the following stages of the calculation:

1. Creating a matrix of objects and features

$$X = [x_{ij}] \quad (i = 1, \dots, n, j = 1, \dots, m) \quad (1)$$

where:

x_{ij} - the value of i -th features (Indicators) of the j -th object (bank)

Indicators in the research were financial ratios of banks (6 ratios). Due to the small number of objects (18 banks) and differentiation as to the value of the balance sheet total, the financial result and the market value, it was considered that the best indicators describing banks will be relative ratios such as: current ratio, solvency ratio, return on shareholder funds (ROE), profit margin, return on assets (ROA) and cost to income ratio (CIR). To avoid skewing the results of all analyzed indicators have relative value. Selection of indicators was subjective and took into account the specificities of value based management of a small bank.

2. The second step of the calculation was to bring the different variables comparable with standardization. As a result of diagnostic standardization of each variable will have a mean value of 0 and standard deviation equal to 1. Standardization was made according to the following formula:

$$z_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - \bar{x}_j}{S_j} \quad (i = 1, \dots, n, j = 1, \dots, m) \quad (2)$$

where:

\bar{x}_j - the arithmetic mean of the j -th features

z_{ij} - standardized value of j -th features of the i -th object

x_{ij} - the value of j -th features of the i -th object

S_j - standard deviation of the j -th features

3. The third step was to estimate the Z_{pj} - Positive Development Pattern (PDP) by setting the maximum value for stimulants and minimum value for destimulants in each col-

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umn of standardized features. Current ratio, solvency ratio, ROE, profit margin, ROA was stimulants. Cost to income ratio (CIR) was destimulant.

4. The next step was calculating the distance of each object from the PDP, taking into account the impact of various strength characteristics of the study examined the phenomenon. Used Euclidean distance was determined by the formula:

$$d_i = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m (z_{ij} - z_{pj})^2} \quad (i = 1, \dots, n) \quad (3)$$

where:

d_i - Euclidean distance from PDP

z_{pj} - Positive Development Pattern (PDP) as a $Max \{ Z_{ij} \}$ for stimulant and $Min \{ Z_{ij} \}$ for destimulant

5. Due to the fact that synthetic variable defined by equation (3) is not normalized, d_i ratio must be change in normativity process. This will lead to changes in preferences of variable, were a larger value will stand to the higher level of the studied phenomenon (competitive position). That synthetic variable will take values in the range from 0 to 1. Formula was as follows:

$$SMD = 1 - \frac{d_i}{\bar{d} + aS_d} \quad (i=1, \dots, n) \quad (4)$$

where:

SMD – Synthetic Measure of Development for i-th object

d_i - weighted Euclidean distance from PDP

\bar{d} - the arithmetic mean of the variable d_i

S_d - standard deviation of the variable d_i .

$$a \geq \frac{\max d_i - \bar{d}}{S_d} \quad (5)$$

a – parameter of inequality

As a result there were created Synthetic Measure of Development - SMD ratio with range from 0 to 1 for each of 18 Banks (9 Polish banks and 9 respectively from peer group) for 2007 (SMD_{2007}) and for 2013 (SMD_{2013}). Sorted from highest to lowest value of SMD ratio became a ranking of competitive position of Polish banks and competitors from peer group.

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Turkiye Bank Halkasi A.S. has $SMD_{2013} = 0,454$. As opposed to 2007 PKO BP S.A. in 2013 had better competitive position than its main competitor. Like in 2007, the worst competitive position in the group of domestic banks reached bank BOŚ S.A. ($SMD_{2013} = 0,147$). However, there was observed a change, because in 2013 in relation to its main competitor (KAS Bank N.V.) BOŚ S.A. achieved a better result. The worst result (the lowest level of SMD) in 2013 was observed for BRD – Groupe Societe Generale S.A. ($SMD_{2013} = 0,000$) what means that this bank was farthest from Positive Development Pattern and achieved the worst relative competitive position in whole group.

Figure 2. SMD ratio of banks in 2013

Resource: Own calculation

From the point of view of the VBM theory and the construction of SMD ratio it is difficult to evaluate the difference in competitive position of one bank to another. In other words, it is not possible to answer to the question of how much better competitive position is one bank from another. However, it is possible to rank the banks in the ranking and comparing them to the main competitor. Evaluating of the Polish banking sector there are noticeable some trends towards competitors. Before financial crises (in 2007) only two of nine Polish banks have higher value of SMD_{2007} ratio (BZWBK S.A. and Getin Noble S.A.) rest of Polish banks have worse competitive position versus main competitor. While after financial crises (in 2013) six domestic banks have better competitive position (PKO BP S.A., Pekao S.A., BZWBK S.A., Millennium S.A., Handlowy S.A. and BOŚ S.A.). This may indicate strengthening competitive position of the Polish banking sector in terms of operating cost ratios, risk ratios and profitability ratios.

Conclusions

The basic problems with the modern banks are mainly related with the level of concentration in the banking sector (size of the assets and market value), the bonuses of the management (costs of salaries and bonuses related to motivate systems) but most of all are related with value creation and competitive position in sector. Hermeticity of the banking system determines that a strengthening competitive position of the bank is probably due to a partial takeover of the banking services market. This is reflected for example in the “banking deposit wars” or proceed mergers or acquisitions in order to achieve customer database of another bank. It is also expressed how banks participate in creation and spreading contemporary financial crises.

Proposed in this paper tool to evaluate the competitive position is not without drawbacks. It does not allow define the difference in the competitive position of the banks designated a specific measure. However, it allows to rank entities from best to worst and allows comparison against its main competitor and to the entire study sample. Without a doubt presented a multi-dimensional ranking is a better tool to assess the competitive position than the ranking based on a single indicator.

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Citation:

Śledzik K., (2015), *Multivariate competitive position analysis in banking sector: Polish banks versus peer group perspective*, Theory of Management 8, (ed.) Stefan Hittmar, Faculty of Management Science and Informatics, University of Zilina,